

ADSORPTIVE REMOVAL OF OIL SPILLS FROM WASTEWATER USING MODIFIED ACTIVATED CARBON

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ABSTRACT

The adsorption method is regarded as one of the most effective current ways for eliminating contaminants, particularly fatty organic hydrocarbon molecules from polluted water. This study uses activated carbon and gold water to eliminate these contaminants. The inclusion of gold atoms inside the activated carbon cavity increases the coal's surface pores while also providing it a positive charge, allowing activated carbon to adsorb and remove negatively charged organic compounds. The coal produced from the trunks of local willow trees scattered throughout the Qassim region is used to remove organic contaminants via chemical adsorption on its surface. To activate the coal, use a gold nitrate solution. The positively charged gold metal ions are bound to the pores and cavities of the coal, resulting in the formation of surface pores and cavities for the positively charged portions, increasing the absorption capacity of activated carbon to absorb negative charged contaminants. The coal is activated with gold particles via a solution of gold nitrate at a concentration of 0.1 normal. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) test revealed an abundance of roughness across the surface of the activated coal, as well as an increase in the coal's surface area and pore volume, while gradual magnification ensured the presence of pores and cavities at all scales on the activated surface. To eliminate negative organic hydrocarbon molecules like heptane and octane from seawater caused by oil spills. Some factors that can affect the efficiency of gold activated coal in removing oily organic compounds, such as the time of coal contact with the heptane and octane solution, pH, and temperature of the mixture, are investigated in order to determine the most suitable conditions for achieving the coal's maximum adsorption capacity. Increasing the temperature of the mixture from 0 to 4 °C results in a considerable rise in the amount of oily compounds, with the maximum adsorption rate measured at 4 °C.

Coal's adsorption capability diminishes with temperature over 4 °C, reaching its lowest value at 50 °C. The results suggest that a friction duration of 30 minutes and a pH of 6.8 are the optimal conditions for obtaining the highest adsorption capacity of activated carbon, 467 mg for heptane and 385 mg for octane. The trials on activated carbon were encouraging in terms of its suitability for the removal of heavy molecular weight contaminants such as the petroleum compounds being studied. Finally, this novel material is affordable and effective, and it is recommended for practical usage at many levels at the national level, including tiny treatment units, particularly in areas close to sources of organic pollution.

Keywords: Adsorption, Oil Spills, Batch Technique, Modified Activated Carbon

Cite this Article: Ali Saleh Albarak, Badryah AlShushan and Saad M Abdelrahman, Adsorptive Removal of Oil Spills from Wastewater Using Modified Activated Carbon, Journal of Advanced Chemical Technology (JACT), 2(1), 2024. pp. 11-20.
https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/JACT/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_1/JACT_02_01_002.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial wastes and sewage plants generate large amounts of oily wastewater and organic pollutants. Oil and its products are major sources of marine pollution due to spills from oil tankers resulting from oil tanker accidents. Various maintenance works in oil refineries, especially those located in marine waters, also increase the possibility of oil leaking into marine waters. The World Health Organization estimates that about 5 million tons of oil and hydrocarbons reach the world's seas and oceans each year. Industrial waste and sewage plants produce a huge amount of oily wastewater and organic contaminants. Oil and its products contribute significantly to maritime pollution as a result of spills from oil tanker accidents. Various maintenance procedures in oil refineries, particularly those located in marine areas, enhance the likelihood of oil leaking into marine seas. The World Health Organization estimates that approximately 5 million tons of oil and hydrocarbons enter the world's seas and oceans each year, [1]. Water contamination caused by human activities is a major environmental hazard. Even modest amounts of petrochemical pollution can have a substantial environmental impact; for example, at a maximum concentration of 5 parts per billion, one liter of gasoline can produce almost 77 million gallons of water unfit for human consumption [2]. Leaks from storage tanks, extraction sites, refineries, and distribution stations contribute significantly to water supply pollution [3]. The petrochemical and metal processing sectors produce the vast bulk of oil combined with water. This oil contains a variety of components, including hydrocarbons, fats, and petroleum fractions including diesel, gasoline, and kerosene. These components can be obtained as oil-in-water emulsions [4]. According to the National Research Council in the United States, approximately 1.3 million tons of oil were spilled into the ocean from recognized sources in 2002 [5]. When oil and water combine, they form an oil-water emulsion or floating film, which must be removed before it may be discharged into the environment. Removing oil-in-water emulsions is a primary focus for many countries seeking to enhance their limited freshwater resources. This includes ongoing research into effective and economical treatment options. This is an attempt to treat tainted water produced by the oil industry. This water can be utilized for a variety of applications after it has been treated to satisfy environmental standards. These include firefighting, irrigation, groundwater replenishment, car washing, and cooling water for power plants. Watering cattle and other livestock is one of its agricultural applications [6]. The US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has established daily and monthly maximums for grease and oil in water of 29 mg/L and 42 mg/L, respectively [7].

As a result, before releasing oily water into the environment, it must first be treated and the oil extracted. To attain this purpose, several technologies have been utilized, including biological processes [8], ultrafiltration and nanofiltration [9], microfiltration [7], adsorption [10], [11], [12], reverse osmosis [13], [14], and electro-flotation. [15], [16]. Advanced oxidation procedures [17], demulsification [18], chemical and electrocoagulation, and agglomeration [19]. However, these approaches can be costly to operate and invest in, and they do have some disadvantages. Among these strategies, adsorption, which involves the adsorption of oil emulsion pollutants on the surface of the absorbent material, has proven to be a successful way for extracting oil from water. Interestingly, adsorption is the most appealing method in underdeveloped nations due to its low cost and excellent efficacy in eliminating various contaminants [20]. Oil adsorption is the process by which oil molecules adhere to the surface of an absorbent [21]. Adsorption is principally governed by physical factors such as van der Waals, hydrogen bonds, steric interactions, polarity, hydrophobicity, dipole-dipole interactions, and π - π interactions [22]. Adsorption is a popular and practical method for treating oily water due to its low cost and simplicity of construction. This approach is based on the attractive interaction of contaminants with the absorbent's outer surface. As a result, pollutant molecules agglomerate on the absorbent's surface rather than penetrating it [23]. Oil adsorption typically involves three steps: (1) dispersion of oil molecules on the absorbent's surface; (2) capillary action to trap oil molecules within the absorbent frame; and (3) agglomeration of oil droplets within the absorbent's porous and rough structure [22]. Adsorption has advantages over other technologies, such as minimal capital costs and design flexibility [24], [25]. Some solid substrates have strong adsorption capabilities, such as clay minerals, zeolites, activated carbon, and fly ash. They've been utilized to eliminate organic contaminants from water. [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33]. Activated carbon has been recommended as a highly effective adsorbent for extracting emulsified oil (gasoline, diesel, and kerosene) from contaminated water [34, 35]. Because activated carbon is inexpensive and readily available in Saudi Arabia's deserts, positively charged gold ion activated carbon was utilized in this study to efficiently adsorb heptane and hexane, two components of petroleum hydrocarbons (diesel oil), from oil-in-water emulsions. The adsorptive properties of the positively charged activated carbon surface were used to remove hydrocarbon contaminants from oil spills, including heptane and negatively charged octane

2.1. Materials and Methods

2.1. Prepare charcoal/carbon activated with gold nitrate:

The activation of charcoal/carbon includes the following steps:

1) - Pretreatment. 2) Activation, or "carbonization" with gold nitrate solution; 3) Removal of the leftover activation solution; and 4) Characterization (or assessment) of the activated material's adsorption capabilities.

2) The charcoal/carbon is rinsed multiple times with ionized water, then steeped in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution for a whole day (to remove the majority of the contaminants) and filtered through filter paper.

3) Carbonization ("activation") with gold nitrate solution: After the preceding procedure, the charcoal/carbon is immersed in 0.1 N phosphoric acid solution for 12 hours to eliminate any impurities and dust. The charcoal or carbon is then rinsed with ionized water again.

Phosphoric acid eliminates all positively charged cations from the charcoal's surface. Then, 50 grams of the resultant charcoal/carbon is immersed in 500 cc of 0.1 N gold nitrate solution and agitated for 24 hours. The charcoal/carbon is then dried at 110 degrees Celsius.

The dried charcoal/carbon is then subjected to "pyrolysis" (or de-volatization by heating in the absence of oxygen) by placing it in a microwave oven set to 700 °C for 50 minutes with a microwave power of 400 W. This method eliminates the volatile compounds, leaving just charcoal/carbon.

2.2. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Test:

The surface morphology of activated charcoal was examined using a Cambridge S-360 scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 16 kV and 2.5 A (0.00025 μm, up to 50,000X magnification). It is used to gather data on the surface topography and composition. The image of the activated carbon surface was obtained at 5000X magnification to show the roughness distribution on the surface, and the specifics of the surface roughness nature were revealed at higher magnifications (10000X, 20000X, and 30000X). 2-3 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectra (FTIR) Test, the purpose of this test is to determine which surface functional groups are present on the charcoal or activated carbon. According to the spectrometer's output results, the infrared transmittance exhibits absorption peaks at specific wavelengths that correlate to particular functional groups. Aliphatic amino groups (N-H), alcohols, phenols, carboxylic acid groups (O-H), carboxylic and carbonyl acid functional branch groups (O-H (COOH)), aldehydes, esters or ketones, carboxyl groups (carbonyl C=O), and peptide amide groups are the functional groups that were present in the test results in this instance.

2.4. Batch technique

The mixing method is regarded one of the best strategies used to achieve the optimal conditions for the highest adsorption rate of pollutants by conducting the following procedures.

1. Prepare activated charcoal by activating it with gold nitrate solution, as previously stated.
2. Make heptane or octane solutions with varying concentrations (from 5 to 20 ppm).
3. Shake 100 ml of heptane or octane solutions with various weights of activated carbon for two hours, then place the mixture in a centrifuge to separate the coal from the liquid solution. Determine the concentration of heptane or octane in the mixture and record the results.
4. Change one parameter and keep the others constant to see how the weight of the coal affects the process of extracting the octane or heptane compound, as well as the friction duration, solution concentration, and pH.
5. Using gas chromatography, determine the concentration of heptane or octane components in their solution before adding activated carbon and after shaking.

Calculate the adsorption capacity using the following law:

$$Q = (C_i - C_f) \times V / m$$

Q : adsorption capacity of activated carbon (milligrams per gram)

C_i : initial concentration of heptane or octane before adding activated carbon

C_f : final concentration of heptane or octane after adding activated carbon, shaking and separation

V : volume of the solution in milliliters

M: Activated charcoal weight in grams

2.5. Reverse adsorption

This experiment is performed after the fundamental adsorption trials (weight, time, pH, and temperature) have been completed to ensure that the pollutants remain stable inside the crystal network forming the surface of the activated charcoal and do not dissolve again in the solution. The activated charcoal loaded with pollutants is shaken in the organic pollutant solvent for two hours before measuring the content of heptane or octane. The decrease in the concentration of pollutants in the solution demonstrates the strength of the link between the activated charcoal and the contaminants.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The presence of the positive gold ion Au^{1+} makes the surface of the activated charcoal a positive surface, which makes it simple for the charcoal to adsorb negatively charged octane and heptane molecules. The clay surface becomes positive when the activated charcoal is activated with the gold ion, which causes a thin coating of positive material to form on the charcoal's surface. The negatively charged octane and heptane molecules can be adsorbed onto the surface of activated carbon. This interpretation is completely consistent with (36). Increasing the amount of the organic ionic compound increases the adsorption effectiveness until reaching the saturation limit at an addition ratio of 0.5 ml per gram of activated carbon, as shown in Figure (1). Figure (2) depicts the influence of activated carbon weight on its efficiency in adsorbing heptane or octane from the mixing solution, demonstrating a constant increase in efficiency as activated carbon weight is added to the mixing mixture. The figure 2 also illustrates that the weight of 0.7 grams of activated carbon per 100 ml of the solution is the best mixing ratio that can produce the highest efficiency that activated carbon can reach, followed by the efficiency of activated carbon. When the effect of shaking activated carbon with heptane or octane solution was investigated, it was discovered that the longer the shaking period, the more heptane or octane was taken from the mixing mixture by the activated carbon, 30 minutes is enough time to remove the maximum amount of heptane and octane. The effect of pH on the mixture of activated carbon, heptane, and octane demonstrates the applicability of the neutral medium for the adsorption process. Figure (3) depicts how increasing the pH affects the efficacy of activated carbon in removing heptane and octane, demonstrating the direct link between them. As a result, the pH must be raised to 6.8 to ensure that activated carbon can remove the heptane or octane molecule at the desired rate. Figure (4) further demonstrates that when the pH rises over a value of 8, adsorption gradually decreases until it reaches its lowest value at pH = 10. Figure 4 depicts the effect of mixture temperature on the effectiveness of activated carbon treated with an organic solvent. The efficiency of activated carbon in adsorption of heptane and octane improves with increasing temperature from 0 to 4 degrees Celsius, with the greatest at 4 degrees Celsius. The effectiveness of activated carbon gradually declines with increasing temperature from 4 to 50 °C. At low temperatures, the chemical potential of heptane and octane decreases, allowing for easier adsorption on the surface of activated carbon, and vice versa.

3.2. Reverse adsorption

The reverse adsorption of the heptane and octane molecules from the surface of activated carbon demonstrates the strength of the link between the heptane and octane compounds and activated carbon. Table No. (3) demonstrates that the degree of reverse adsorption decreases and approaches zero, demonstrating that the speed of adsorption increases as a forward reaction compared to reverse adsorption as a reverse reaction in a mixture of activated carbon, heptane, and octane.

The absence of reverse adsorption is proof of the chemical and physical connection between activated carbon and heptane and octane, as well as the fixing of the heptane and octane molecule within the activated carbon's crystal network. The following explanations explain activated carbon's great ability to eliminate organic contaminants heptane and octane:

1. The process of activating activated carbon with gold nitrate results in staining the surface with a positive charge and altering the crystal structure with wider gaps that can adsorb negative organic molecules, as is the case with the two compounds under study.
2. Adsorption rate increases owing to positively charged edges on the surface of the activated carbon particle, which is related to the presence of the positive gold ion, as the particles attract and cluster together when the negatively charged faces clash with the positively charged edges.

3. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM) TEST:

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) pictures of the activated carbon surface at increasing magnifications of (d) 5000X, (c) 10000X, (b) 20000X, and (a) 30000X are displayed in Figures 5. When viewed at 5000X magnification, Figure (d) demonstrates how the grinding process has left both regular and irregular cavities on the activated carbon's outer surface. Figure (c) has double the magnification of Figure (d), while Figure (b) has twice the magnification of Figure (c). In the meantime, Figure (a) has a 50% higher magnification than Figure (b). The removal of surface minerals and organic substances processes produced levels of fine and deeper pores and abnormalities at all scales, as demonstrated by this increasing magnification during the activation and “thermal decomposition” processes. In addition, the four photos clearly show a consistent pore system. These pictures also reveal the presence of numerous well-developed pores, which are linked to the high concentration of lingual cellulose structures, as seen in Tables 1 and 2. Magnification revealed deeper pores inside the vesicles as well as voids within the activated charcoal's surface pore network. All of these surface holes help to increase the adsorption capacity of activated charcoal.

Table (1 a) the physic-chemical properties activated carbon

Parameter	Value
pH	6.02
Moister content (%)	14.87
Ash content (%)	1.08
E.C. (dS/m)	0.75
Specific gravity	1.83
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.62
Porosity (%)	51.03
Matter soluble in water (%)	18.24

Table(1b) the elemental properties of of activated carbon

Parameter	Value
C (%) by weight	0.36
H (%) by weight	7.02
N (%) by weight	0.58
O (%) by weight	284.0
Surface area (m ² /g)	1028
Iodine number	917
Pore Volume (%)	89.21

Table (2) composition analysis of activated carbon

Component	weight %
Moisture content	15.02
Pectin	9.54
Lignin	21.18
Hemo-cellulose	9.25
Cellulose	31.82
Calcium, as Ca ²⁺	0.93
Sodium, as Na ⁺	0.35
Potassium, as K ⁺	0.43
Magnesium, as Mg ²⁺	0.32
Ash	11.05

Table (3) Reverse adsorption of octane and heptane on modified activated carbon

compound	Reverse adsorption %		
		C _i ppm	C _f ppm
Heptane	0.03	0.23	0.26
Octane	0.7	0.35	0.41

Fig. 5, Scanning Electron Microscope of activated carbon (SEM)

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Activated charcoal that has been chemically treated with gold nitrate solvent is used to treat water that contains negatively charged oily organic compounds because it has demonstrated a high level of effectiveness in eliminating the organic contaminants found in the study.

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Adsorptive Removal of Oil Spills from Wastewater Using Modified Activated Carbon

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Citation: Ali Saleh Albarak, Badryah AlShushan and Saad M Abdelrahman, Adsorptive Removal of Oil Spills from Wastewater Using Modified Activated Carbon, *Journal of Advanced Chemical Technology (JACT)*, 2(1), 2024. pp. 11-20

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